

A fault-tolerant clustering algorithm for processing data from multiple streams

Abraham Otero ^{1*}, Paulo Félix ², David G. Márquez ¹, Constantino A. García ¹, Gabriel Caffarena ¹

¹ *Department of Information Technology, Escuela Politécnica Superior, Universidad San Pablo-CEU, CEU Universities, Campus Montepríncipe, Boadilla del Monte, Madrid 28668, Spain.*

² *Centro de Investigación en Tecnologías de Información (CiTIUS), University of Santiago de Compostela, 15782 Santiago de Compostela, Spain.*

* *Correspondence: abraham.otero@gmail.com; aotero@ceu.es.*

Abstract

Nowadays often multiple sensors provide real-time data about the same process. However, most data stream analysis algorithms work over a single feature vector. A common approach to overcome this is to combine the features extracted from each sensor into a single vector. The more sensors monitor a process, the more likely there is a malfunction or delay in data transmission. Hence the interest in developing algorithms capable of handling missing data or incorporating delayed data when it becomes available. This work presents a dynamic ensemble clustering algorithm based on evidence accumulation that can process multiple data streams. Each algorithm of the ensemble only processes one data stream, and obtaining the final partition does not require that data from all the streams is available. Therefore, final results can be provided even when there are sensor malfunctions or network delays. Furthermore, if delayed data arrives it can be used to extract evidence from the moment of arrival onwards. The algorithm was applied to identify arrhythmias over 71 standard 12-lead electrocardiogram recordings, achieving a $0.314\% \pm 0.010$ error rate. The strategies of combining all the leads in a single feature vector or working with each lead independently were compared, obtaining better results in the second case.

Keywords: Dynamic Clustering, Ensemble algorithms, Evidence accumulation, Arrhythmia

1. Introduction

Advances in communication technologies at the level of local area networks, with protocols such as Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, Bluetooth Low Energy, Ant+, and Zigbee, as well as the increasing adoption of 4G-5G technologies have considerably eased real time data transmission at long distances [42]. Simultaneously, advances in electronic technology, including long-duration batteries, size reduction, and cost reduction, have increased the prevalence of wireless sensors that take continuous measurements of industrial processes, computer networks, traffic, weather, or human health and lifestyle, to name a few [7, 14, 37, 45].

The data recorded by these sensors is often used to support decisions that have to be made in real time. Therefore, the data has to be analyzed as it arrives, not being possible to store it for later analysis. Even when the decisions do not have to be made in real time, in some cases the high volume of the data prevents its storage in main memory; therefore algorithms that are able to analyze the data with a single pass are required [14]. This type of data is usually known as a data stream or streaming data. A data stream is a large, potentially unbounded, ordered sequence of data that must be accessed in order and that can be read only once [39]. Data streams often represent some evolving process whose data arrives through a network connection, frequently from several sources.

Due to the low cost and wide availability of both sensors and wireless communication technologies, it is common that multiple sensors provide real-time data about the same process. Each of these sensors could be considered as a source of a physical data stream. However, most of the algorithms published in the literature to analyze stream data work over a single data stream [8, 25, 41, 42], by combining the data from several sensors into a single “logical” data stream. This is usually achieved through the extraction of the relevant features from the data of each sensor, and their combination into a single feature vector [40]. This can be a good solution if the data acquisition and transmission from the sensors are reliable, and it can be expected that all the measurements for the

30 same object obtained from the different sensors will be available approximately
31 at the same time. These conditions are only met if there are no malfunctions in
32 any of the sensors or the transmission networks, nor delays in the transmission.

33 In the event that the data from a sensor relative to an object is lost, due to
34 sensor malfunctioning or networking problems, most of the algorithms published
35 in the literature would have to discard this object, even if data from other
36 sensors is available and could shed some light about the decision to be made
37 [25]. Furthermore, if the data from a sensor suffers significant delays, it would
38 be ideal to be able to make the best decision possible with the data available at
39 that time, and review those decisions if in the future the delayed data arrives.
40 Of course, in many applications it is very difficult to distinguish between delayed
41 data that will eventually arrive, and data that has been irrevocably lost [9]. In
42 the near future, it is expected that the number of sensors used to monitor a
43 single process will grow [18, 21]. Given that each sensor increases the likelihood
44 of data loss due to malfunction, noise, or of data transmission delays, these
45 problems are bound to worsen in the future. Hence the interest in developing
46 data stream analysis algorithms which are capable of handling missing data, or
47 incorporating delayed data when it becomes available.

48 Ensemble algorithms [20, 25] could be an elegant framework to address these
49 problems. One or more algorithms of the ensemble could independently analyze
50 the data from each sensor, to be later integrated with the results of the analysis
51 of the other sensors. If at any given time there is no data from a sensor or
52 a set of sensors, because it has been lost or it is delayed, the algorithms of
53 the ensemble can analyze the data of the remaining sensors. As long as the
54 mechanism that integrates the ensemble results does not require that results
55 from all the sensors are available, a decision considering the data available at
56 any time can be provided. Ideally, this integration mechanism should be able to
57 handle data that arrives delayed. An additional advantage of this approach is
58 the possibility of creating distributed and collaborative implementations of the
59 ensemble [13], enabling edge-oriented computing architectures [47].

60 In the literature there are multistream classification algorithms designed

61 for scenarios where there are two or more independent non stationary data
62 streams, and where at least one of them is labeled. Some of these approaches are
63 based on ensembles and each stream is processed independently [20]. However,
64 ensemble stream clustering algorithms usually group all the available data in a
65 single feature vector that is shared by the different algorithms of the ensemble,
66 even when applied to problems in which data arrives from several physical data
67 sources that may be geographically dispersed [5, 29].

68 Yang and Chen [46] developed an ensemble clustering algorithm where K-
69 means is applied over different feature vectors that represent the same object.
70 A set of partitions are generated from these representations, and they are evalu-
71 ated by a series of clustering validity indices. The three best partitions according
72 to this evaluation are selected to generate the final partition through an agree-
73 ment function. However, this algorithm assumes that the data being analyzed
74 arrives from a single physical data stream, although different representations of
75 each object are extracted from that stream. Márquez et al. [32] present a static
76 ensemble clustering algorithm that generates partitions from the data extracted
77 from different sensors without the need to combine the information from each
78 sensor into a single feature vector, and integrates these partitions into a final
79 partition using a voting mechanism. This algorithm is applied to the problem
80 of grouping beats according to their morphological family. When the ensemble
81 of partitions is generated using the features obtained from each electrocardio-
82 gram (ECG) lead separately and then the results are integrated, better results
83 were achieved in the morphological beat identification task compared with the
84 strategy of combining all the features in a single feature vector.

85 This work presents a dynamic clustering algorithm that can process multi-
86 ple data streams in real time, and it can provide partial clustering results at
87 any moment. If one or more of these streams are not available, the algorithm
88 can work over the available ones. If delayed data from some of the streams
89 arrives at some time in the future, it can be incorporated into the generation
90 of the partitions from the moment of arrival. The algorithm was applied to the
91 identification of arrhythmias in real time over the 12-lead Holter ECG record-

ings of the St.Petersburg Institute of Cardiological Technics 12-lead Arrhythmia Database, achieving a $0.314\% \pm 0.010$ error rate. The capability of the algorithm to integrate multiple streams without degrading its performance was tested by running the algorithm using an increasing number of leads (from 1 up to 12). The more leads available the lower error rate (statistically significant) was obtained. Tests have also been executed where a single feature vector was created with the features extracted from all the ECG leads (the classic approach in machine learning). This approach yielded statistically significant worst results when compared with equivalent tests where the features of each lead were processed separately.

Section 2 explains how ensembles of partitions are created using data from multiple data streams, and how evidence is extracted from the partitions. Section 3 presents the algorithm, which we have named Evolving Evidence Accumulation Clustering (EEAC), together with an analysis of its computational complexity. An application of the algorithm to the problem of real-time beat morphological identification is presented in section 4. The results of this application are presented in the section 5, together with a series of tests designed to study the properties of the EEAC algorithm, along with a comparison with two of the most widely used stream clustering algorithms: Clustream [7], and Clustree [24]. Section 6 discusses both the application to the cardiology domain, as well as the general properties of the algorithm. Finally, conclusions are drawn.

2. Evidence generation

2.1. Previous definitions

We shall define O as a open-ended ordered sequence of objects $O = \{o_1, o_2, \dots\}$ with an unknown number of total objects, where the object o_i has arrived in the position i . In this work, the term object is used to denote the entities from which the features used to create the computational representation of the problem are extracted. Objects may be defined by a specific event (the occurrence of a heartbeat, the start of a network connection, the publication of a com-

121 ment in a social media network...), or by a time window of fixed duration (a
 122 set of measurements related to a company's LAN traffic during each second,
 123 minute-by-minute power production and consumption of different nodes of an
 124 electrical grid...). Thus, the arrival time of consecutive objects needs not to be
 125 equidistant. If the index of the last available object of the sequence is n , we
 126 shall denote all the objects available when o_n arrives as $O^n = \{o_1, o_2, \dots, o_n\}$.

127 We shall assume that the information related to each object o_i is provided
 128 by from a set, possibly composed of a single element, of data streams $\mathcal{S} =$
 129 $\{s_1, s_2, \dots, s_e\}$. Each of these data streams can contribute one or more features
 130 for each object o_i . We shall denote by $x_i^{k,:} = (x_i^{k,1}, x_i^{k,2}, x_i^{k,3}, \dots)$ all the features
 131 of the object o_i that are provided by the data stream s_k . We will denote the
 132 feature vector of the object o_i as $\mathbf{x}_i = (x_i^{1,:}, x_i^{2,:}, \dots, x_i^{e,:})$, where e is the total
 133 number of data streams. The different pieces of information about the object
 134 o_i that arise from different data streams may be available at different points in
 135 time, and for some objects a given data stream may not provide any information
 136 (due to sensor malfunction or too much noise in the readings). Therefore, it is
 137 possible that at a given time we have to work with incomplete feature vectors
 138 whose missing information may arrive later, or it may never arrive.

139 This situation could correspond to a scenario in which multiple sensors
 140 are recording related information (for example, multiple physiological sensors
 141 recording information from a patient). Each of these sensors would be a differ-
 142 ent data stream. Due to technical problems, the sensor corresponding with the
 143 data stream s_k may stop recording data over a period of time, or it may record
 144 measurements with too much noise to provide any useful information. However,
 145 if measurements from other sensors are available, we would like to cluster an
 146 object o_i recorded while the data from s_k was not available, despite lacking the
 147 features $x_i^{k,:}$. If the sensors in question were sending the data over a wireless
 148 network (for example, a patient who is being telemonitored [37]), it is possible
 149 that at a certain time the information from a sensor s_k is not available due to
 150 network delays, but the information from all other sensors, or a subset of them,
 151 is available. At this point, we may be interested in clustering the data using

152 the available features. If at some later time past data from s_k arrives and the
 153 features $x_i^{k,:}$ become available, henceforth we would like to exploit this cuando
 154 Ana tres grupos figure y prefiero no hay information when clustering o_i .

155 In practice, the data analyst may decide to combine several physical data
 156 streams (for example, measurements from several sensors) into one logical data
 157 stream s_k ; in this case, the set of features $x_i^{k,:}$ would comprise features extracted
 158 from all those physical data streams. However, we shall assume that either all
 159 the data from the different physical data streams combined in s_k is available
 160 at a given time instant, or none is available; i.e., either all the features $x_i^{k,:}$ are
 161 available, or none is.

162 The result of applying a clustering algorithm over the sequence of objects
 163 $O^n = \{o_1, o_2, \dots, o_n\}$ and the features $x_i^{k,:}$ arising from the data stream s_k
 164 will be a partition $P_k^n = \{A_{k,1}^n, A_{k,2}^n, \dots, A_{k,g}^n\}$. This partition distributes the
 165 objects available in g groups, where $A_{k,j}^n$ represents the group j of the partition
 166 P_k^n . If the features provided by s_k for some previous object o_i , $i < n$, are not
 167 available when o_n arrives (i.e., $x_i^{k,:}$ is not available), o_i will not be present in
 168 P_k^n . However, if the features $x_i^{k,:}$ have become available when a later object o_m ,
 169 $m > n$, arrives, then the partition P_k^m , as well as the later ones, can contain
 170 the object o_i . No assumption is made about the number of groups g of each
 171 partition, which could vary between partitions.

172 We shall define an *ensemble* over O^n as a set of different partitions $E^n =$
 173 $\{P_{1,1}^n, P_{1,2}^n, \dots, P_{2,1}^n, P_{2,2}^n, \dots, P_{k,1}^n, P_{k,2}^n, \dots, P_{e,1}^n, P_{e,2}^n, \dots\}$, where $P_{k,h}^n$ represents
 174 the h partition obtained over the features of the data stream s_k . We shall denote
 175 by p the total number of partitions of E^n . Combining all these partitions we
 176 can obtain the final partition P_*^n containing all the objects available up to o_n .
 177 An object o_i will belong to the final partition P_*^n as long as its information is
 178 available from a single data stream s_k ; however, o_i might not be present in any
 179 given partition $P_{k,h}^n$ if the features $x_i^{k,:}$ were not available when o_n arrived. In
 180 the next section we will describe how the partitions of E^n are generated, and
 181 how evidence is extracted from them.

182 *2.2. Partition Generation*

183 Ensemble clustering techniques require the generation of different data par-
184 titions. Some common strategies for generating them are using different
185 representations of the data, applying data alteration techniques such as sam-
186 pling or bagging, using different clustering algorithms, or running the same al-
187 gorithm with different parameters. These ensembles of partitions can overcome
188 the limitations of the individual partitions, abstracting the different represen-
189 tations, clustering algorithms or parametrizations and extracting the mutual
190 information of the different data partitions.

191 Due to its simplicity and computational efficiency, the K-means algorithm
192 is probably the most widely used clustering algorithm. The inflexibility on the
193 shape of the clusters that it forms, which are always hyper-spherical, prevents
194 its usage for the identification of clusters with arbitrary shapes, making it un-
195 suitable for applications which need to model complex shapes. This is probably
196 its major limitation. However, by combining several executions of the K-means
197 algorithm, it is possible to overcome this limitation and represent clusters of
198 virtually any shape [16].

199 Although the EEAC technique does not require the usage of a particular
200 clustering algorithm for generating the partitions, in this paper, K-means shall
201 be used for partition generation due to its reduced computational cost. K-means
202 shall be run with arbitrary initializations for the initial centroids, and with a
203 random number of clusters in the interval $[\sqrt{n}/2, \sqrt{n}]$ for each execution, where
204 n is the number of objects to be partitioned. This range for the number of
205 clusters has shown to be suitable for real-world applications [16, 32].

206 *2.3. Evidence Extraction and Combination*

207 Among the different approaches for combining the results of different data
208 partitions in the ensemble clustering literature [16, 34], EEAC uses an evidence
209 accumulation approach based on a voting strategy that gathers information
210 about those pairs of objects that appear in the same cluster of a given partition
211 [6]. This strategy permits combining partitions with different number of clusters,

212 even if they do not share the same objects. This last property is essential for
 213 the algorithm EEAC, since an object o_i could be absent from the partition $P_{k,h}^n$,
 214 $i < n$, if the features $x_i^{k,:}$ were not available when o_n arrived.

215 In the evidence accumulation paradigm, the co-occurrence of two objects o_i
 216 and o_j in the same cluster of a partition $P_{k,h}^n \in E^n$ is treated as a vote (a piece
 217 of evidence) to both objects belonging to the same cluster in the final partition.
 218 If two objects belong to the same “natural” cluster, they will likely be assigned
 219 to the same cluster in most partitions of E^n . Hence, the co-occurrence of a pair
 220 of objects o_i and o_j in the same cluster of an individual partition of E^n will be
 221 a vote towards both objects belonging to the same final partition. Votes shall
 222 be stored in the corresponding cell of the *evidence matrix* Ω , whose size is $n \times n$,
 223 being n the number of objects available. The Ω matrix will be:

$$\Omega_{(i,j)} = q_{ij}, \quad (1)$$

224 where q_{ij} is the number of times that o_i and o_j were assigned to the same cluster
 225 in the partitions of E^n .

226 Since we may be working with incomplete feature vectors, the number of
 227 partitions of E^n in which the pair of objects o_i and o_j are present may vary
 228 depending on the objects, regardless them being assigned to the same cluster
 229 or not. This hinders the interpretation of Ω ; the meaning of $\Omega_{i,j} = 10$ differs if
 230 o_i and o_j were both present in 10 different partitions, or in 1000 partitions. We
 231 shall define the matrix Φ of size $n \times n$ as:

$$\Phi_{(i,j)} = u_{ij}, \quad (2)$$

232 where u_{ij} is the number of partitions of E^n where both objects were present,
 233 regardless them being assigned to the same cluster or not. If Ω is divided by Φ
 234 cell by cell, the percentage of times that two objects were grouped together in
 235 all partitions where they both were present is obtained. We will define a matrix
 236 Ψ that stores these percentages:

$$\Psi_{(i,j)} = \frac{\Omega_{(i,j)}}{\Phi_{(i,j)}}. \quad (3)$$

237 **3. Evolving Evidence Accumulation Clustering**

238 Every time a new object arrives, the EEAC algorithm extracts evidence
239 through the generation of new partitions. This would result in the size of the
240 matrix Ω of Eq. 1 increasing by one more row and one column each time a
241 new object arrives. Therefore, given that we are working with an open-ended
242 sequence of objects, the algorithm would gradually degrade its performance as
243 this matrix grows. To cope with this issue we shall work over a vector $V =$
244 $\{v_1, v_2, \dots, v_l\}$ of constant size l that acts as a prototype array [40] representing
245 all objects processed up to the present instant. Its size is a parameter that
246 determines the size of Ω and the number of objects with which the partitions
247 will be created. Each $v_i \in V$ could be an object of O^n , or a summary of a subset
248 of objects of O^n . Section 3.2 will present how this summary is made. The term
249 *element* shall be used to refer to each component of the vector V , while the
250 term *object* shall be used to refer to the components of O^n .

251 *3.1. Initialization stage*

252 While the number of objects n of O^n is less than l (initialization stage),
253 each new object is stored in V (see Algorithm 1, line 1; henceforth when a line
254 number is referenced, it will be assumed that it belongs to Algorithm 1). No
255 evidence shall be collected until the vector V is full. Once l objects have arrived,
256 p_{init} partitions are generated, and evidence is collected from them (Eq. 1). The
257 matrices Φ and Ψ are also initialized accordingly (Eqs. 2 and 3, line 4). Finally,
258 a vector Y is initialized in such a way that the l first elements of V are mapped
259 to the l first objects of $O^{n=l}$: $Y = (y_1 = 1, y_2 = 2, \dots, y_l = l)$. This vector will
260 maintain a mapping between each object of O^n and the element of the vector
261 V that represents it.

262 *3.2. Dynamic update of the partitions and the evidence*

263 After the initialization, a loop begins to process objects dynamically (line
264 6). When a new object arrives it is necessary to make room in V to store it. To
265 this end, the two most similar elements v_i and v_j of V are selected and merged.

266 *3.2.1. Finding the two most similar elements*

Given that Ψ is a similarity matrix, the pair of most similar elements of V can be found by looking for its maximum. Given the symmetry of the matrix, only cells above the diagonal need to be considered:

$$I = \{(i, j) \mid (i, j) = \operatorname{argmax}_{h,k}(\Psi_{(h,k)}), h < k\}, \quad (4)$$

267 where I is a list containing the pairs of most similar elements. If I contains more
 268 than one pair, the tie must be broken. To this end, the grouping with the rest
 269 of the elements shall be considered. If v_i tends to group with the same elements
 270 as v_j , both elements are similar. Each row (or column) of Ψ represents the
 271 grouping of an element with the rest of the elements of V . Therefore, comparing
 272 two columns (or rows), the grouping of two elements can be compared. For this
 273 comparison any metric may be used; in our implementation we have chosen the
 274 Euclidean distance:

$$J = \{(i, j) \mid (i, j) = \operatorname{argmin}_{h,k}(\operatorname{distance}(\Psi_{(h,:)}, \Psi_{(k,:)}), \forall (h, k) \in I)\}. \quad (5)$$

275 where J is a list containing the most similar pairs. If J still contains more than
 276 one pair, the Euclidean distance (or some other metric) between the elements
 277 of each remaining pair will be used to find the most similar pair:

$$K = \{(i, j) \mid (i, j) = \operatorname{argmin}_{h,k}(\operatorname{distance}(v_h, v_k)/d_{h,k}), \forall (h, k) \in J)\}. \quad (6)$$

278 where $d_{h,k}$ is the number of features that are present in both v_h and v_k . In the
 279 calculation of the distance, should any of the features of v_h or v_k not be available
 280 (due to data loss or transmission delays), they will be ignored. Therefore, in
 281 order to be able to compare the distances calculated with different number
 282 of features, they are divided by the number of features that are not missing
 283 (the same approximation is used during the initialization stage in case there is
 284 missing data). In case there still were more than one pair of elements in K , one
 285 shall be chosen at random.

286 *3.2.2. Merging the two most similar elements*

287 Once the pair (v_i, v_j) of most similar elements of V has been found, they
 288 are merged to make room for the new object. The element resulting from the
 289 merger is calculated as the mean of the feature vectors of the two elements (line
 290 8). If any of the features is missing for one of the elements, the value of the
 291 other element's feature will be used for the merged feature. If any feature is
 292 missing for both elements, it will also be missing in the merged element. This
 293 element will occupy the position of v_i in V : $v_i \leftarrow \text{mean}(v_i, v_j)$. Then, Y is
 294 updated to change all the elements pointing to j to point to i , the position of
 295 the merged element (line 9).

The matrices Ω and Φ also need to be updated. The evidence and partition count of the pair of elements will be assigned to the merged object.

$$\left(\Omega_{(:,i)} = \Omega_{(i,:)} \right) \leftarrow \Omega_{(i,:)} + \Omega_{(j,:)}, \quad (7)$$

$$\left(\Phi_{(:,i)} = \Phi_{(i,:)} \right) \leftarrow \Phi_{(i,:)} + \Phi_{(j,:)}. \quad (8)$$

296 Then, the new object is stored in the position corresponding of v_j , $v_j \leftarrow o_j$,
 297 and Y is updated in such a way that $y_n \leftarrow j$ (line 11). The element v_j is
 298 new and, at this moment, there is no evidence about it. Consequently, the
 299 corresponding columns and rows of Ω and Φ are zeroed (line 12).

300 *3.3. Collection of evidence*

301 Once the new object has been added to V , evidence shall be collected by
 302 generating p partitions, and the matrix Ω is updated:

$$\Omega_{(i,j)} = \Omega_{(i,j)} + q_{ij}, \quad (9)$$

303 where q_{ij} is the number of times that v_i and v_j have appeared in the same
 304 cluster in the p partitions. The matrix Φ is also updated:

$$\Phi_{(i,j)} = \Phi_{(i,j)} + u_{ij}. \quad (10)$$

Algorithm 1 O^n is an open-ended ordered sequence of objects, l is the size of the vector V , p_{init} is the number of initialization partitions and p is the number of partitions to generate for each new object.

Require: $O^n = \{o_1, o_2, \dots\}$, l , p_{init} , p

Ensure: P_* final partition of data

- 1: Initialize V with first l objects of O^n , $V = \{v_1 \leftarrow o_1, v_2 \leftarrow o_2, \dots, v_l \leftarrow o_l\}$
- 2: Generate p_{init} partitions with the elements of V
- 3: Extract evidence and accumulate it in Ω {#Eq. (1)}
- 4: Initialize Φ and Ψ {#Eqs. (2) and (3)}
- 5: Initialize Y , $Y = (y_1 \leftarrow 1, y_2 \leftarrow 2, \dots, y_l \leftarrow l)$
- 6: **while** new object o_n **do**
- 7: $(v_i, v_j) \leftarrow \text{SearchMostSimilarPair}(V, \Psi)$ {#Eqs. (4), (5), and (6)}
- 8: $v_i \leftarrow \text{mean}(v_i, v_j)$
- 9: Update Y changing every $y_m = j$ by $y_m \leftarrow i$
- 10: Update Φ and Ω {#Eqs. (7) and (8)}
- 11: $v_j \leftarrow o_n$; $y_n \leftarrow j$
- 12: $\Omega_{(j,:)} \leftarrow 0$, $\Omega_{(:,j)} \leftarrow 0$, $\Phi_{(j,:)} \leftarrow 0$, $\Phi_{(:,j)} \leftarrow 0$
- 13: Generate p partitions with the elements of V
- 14: Extract evidence and update Ω , Φ and Ψ {#Eqs. (9), (10), and (3)}
- 15: **if** (Final partition required) **then**
- 16: $P_*^V \leftarrow \text{hierarchical.cluster}(\Psi)$
- 17: $P_*^n \leftarrow P_*^V$
- 18: **for all** $(v_i) \in P_*^V$ **do**
- 19: $H = \{\}$
- 20: **for** $j = 1$ **to** n **do**
- 21: **if** $(y_j = i)$ **then**
- 22: $H \leftarrow \{H, (o_j)\}$
- 23: **end if**
- 24: **end for**
- 25: $P_*^n \text{.replace}(v_i) \text{.by}(H)$
- 26: **end for** {#Final partition available}
- 27: **end if**
- 28: $n = n + 1$
- 29: **end while**

305 with u_{ij} being the number of partitions where both v_i and v_j were present,
 306 regardless them being assigned to the same cluster or not. Finally, Ψ is updated
 307 with Eq. (3).

308 The choice of p must be made carefully since these partitions are created
 309 every time a new object arrives, so it significantly impacts the performance of
 310 the algorithm. When choosing this parameter, it should be borne in mind that
 311 it may not be necessary to choose a high p value to generate enough evidence
 312 to confidently group o_n from the beginning. This would only be necessary if at
 313 that precise moment it is required to know the cluster to which o_n belongs to.
 314 When the object o_{n+1} arrives, p partitions will be generated again, and these
 315 partitions will also contribute evidence for o_n , and the same happens every time
 316 a new object arrives. Thus, if an immediate clustering for o_n is not necessary,
 317 gathering evidence with a low number of partitions should suffice.

318 3.4. Obtaining the final partition

319 The last step is executed only when a partial result of the clustering of the
 320 objects processed up to a given moment is necessary (line 15). The matrix Ψ is
 321 a similarity matrix over which any clustering algorithm designed for similarity
 322 matrices (e.g., hierarchical clustering or Partitioning Around Medoids) may be
 323 applied. In our implementation we have chosen a hierarchical single linkage
 324 clustering algorithm [12] for its capability of handling non-elliptical shapes, and
 325 because it allows the user to determine the number of clusters of the final parti-
 326 tion by cutting the dendrogram at the appropriate height. In order to show the
 327 final result in terms of the objects of O^n , the mapping information stored in Y
 328 can be used (lines 18-26). To this end, each element v_i of P_*^V shall be replaced
 329 by the objects $\{o_a, o_b, o_c, \dots\}$ such that:

$$\forall o_i \in \{o_a, o_b, o_c, \dots\} : y_j = i; \quad (11)$$

330 thus, obtaining the final partition P_*^n over the objects of O^n . The diagram in
 331 Figure 1 summarizes the main steps of the algorithm.

Figure 1: Diagram summarizing the main steps of the EEAC algorithm. Data stream 2 is not providing data for the object o_n that is being processed; hence the features $x_n^{2,:}$ are missing.

332 3.5. Computational complexity analysis

333 To analyze the computational complexity of the algorithm, we will focus on
 334 the loop that processes the objects one by one, since the algorithm initialization
 335 process only has to be run once. The complexity of the operations of finding
 336 and merging the pair of most similar elements is dominated by the traversal
 337 of a matrix of size $l \times l$ (see Eq. 4), since the rest of the operations involve a
 338 single pass through lists of much smaller size than the matrix (see Eqs. 5 and
 339 6). Therefore their computational complexity is $\mathcal{O}(l^2)$.

340 K-means is used to generate the partitions. Its complexity is $\mathcal{O}(l \cdot d \cdot i \cdot k)$,
 341 where l is the number of elements, d is the number of dimensions of the feature
 342 vectors, i is the number of iterations before converging, and k is the number
 343 of clusters. d is constant and typically much smaller than l , and i is typically
 344 set to a maximum value (100 in our implementation, although convergence is
 345 often achieved much earlier). The maximum value of k in our algorithm is \sqrt{l} .

346 Consequently, the complexity of K-means can be approximated by $\mathcal{O}(l \cdot \sqrt{l})$. K-
 347 means needs to be run p times (the number of partitions to generate) for each
 348 iteration. Therefore, the computational complexity of generating the partitions
 349 is $\mathcal{O}(p \cdot l \cdot \sqrt{l})$.

350 The extraction of the evidence requires traversing matrices of size $l \times l$ a
 351 constant number of times (two times) (see Eqs. 9 and 10). This has a complexity
 352 of $\mathcal{O}(l^2)$ for each of the p partitions, which yields a computational complexity of
 353 $\mathcal{O}(p \cdot l^2)$. The last step is the extraction of the final partition using a hierarchical
 354 clustering algorithm, whose computational complexity is [12]: $\mathcal{O}(l^2 \cdot \log(l))$.
 355 Hence the computational complexity of all the steps of the algorithm is:

$$\mathcal{O}(l^2) + \mathcal{O}(p \cdot l \cdot \sqrt{l}) + \mathcal{O}(p \cdot l^2) + \mathcal{O}(l^2 \cdot \log(l)) \approx \mathcal{O}((p + \log(l)) \cdot l^2). \quad (12)$$

356 The extraction of the final partition is an optional step in the algorithm,
 357 which does not need to be run on each iteration. It is reasonable to assume that
 358 in most cases it will not be necessary to provide a final partition every time a
 359 single object arrives. If we ignore this contribution, Eq. 12 becomes $\mathcal{O}(p \cdot l^2)$.

360 The loop must be executed for each new object, thus the overall complexity
 361 of processing n objects is $\mathcal{O}((n - l) \cdot p \cdot l^2)$ (the first l objects are used for
 362 initialization outside the loop). For large values of n :

$$\mathcal{O}((n - l) \cdot p \cdot l^2) \approx \mathcal{O}(n \cdot p \cdot l^2). \quad (13)$$

363 Regarding the storage space required by the algorithm, the only data struc-
 364 ture that does not have a constant size is the vector Y . Every time a new object
 365 arrives it is necessary to reserve an additional position in Y to store a single
 366 integer (the position of V where o^n has been stored). All other data structures
 367 of the algorithm have a constant size, being the largest ones the matrices Ω , Φ
 368 and Ψ , of size $l \times l$. Therefore, the storage requirements for large amounts of
 369 data ($n \gg l^2$) is given by $\mathcal{O}(n)$.

370 4. Application to heart beat clustering

371 An ECG lead is a measure of the electrical activity of the heart measured
372 as the difference in potential between two points of the patient's body. The
373 electrode configuration most used in electrocardiography is the standard 12-lead
374 ECG, where each lead records the electrical activity of the heart from a different
375 angle [19]. The information provided by different leads is complementary, being
376 each a different source of information about the functioning of the heart.

377 While beat detection over the ECG is a problem solved with an acceptable
378 degree of satisfaction (sensitivity of about 99.9% over the reference databases
379 [43]), the identification of the heartbeat morphology is still an open prob-
380 lem. Different morphologies in the beat are related to different abnormalities
381 in the conduction and propagation of the electrical stimulus throughout the
382 myocardium; i.e., different types of arrhythmias (see Fig 2). Automatic mor-
383 phological identification is an important aid for the expert cardiologist in the
384 interpretation of the ECG, especially in long-term recordings (1-3 days), which
385 are necessary in those cases where symptoms appear intermittently. Visual
386 inspection of these long-term recordings by cardiologists is tedious and time-
387 consuming; the average human heart beats about 100,000 times a day, and up
388 to 12 leads provide complementary information for each beat. Reliable auto-
389 matic real-time ECG analysis could permit routinely out-of-hospital monitoring
390 of patients, enabling a more proactive model of healthcare where ECGs could be
391 recorded in non-symptomatic patients for the early identification of pathologies,
392 instead of a reactive model where the monitoring starts once the patient has
393 begun to present symptoms [38]. Hence the interest in providing computational
394 support for real time ECG analysis [19].

395 4.1. *St. Petersburg Institute of Cardiological Technics 12-Lead Arrhythmia* 396 *Database*

397 The St. Petersburg Institute of Cardiological Technics 12-lead Arrhythmia
398 Database (INCARTDB) consists of 75 long-term Holter recordings sampled at a

Figure 2: Fragment of the recording I58; note how lead V4 shows a constant output. Normal beats are marked with blue dots; approximately in the middle of the recording a ventricular beat marked with a V is shown.

399 frequency of 257 Hz from 32 different patients. It is widely used in the scientific
 400 literature because it is one of the few available databases with 12 leads annotated
 401 beat by beat [2, 3, 23, 28, 44]. The mean age of patients is 58 years and none
 402 of the patients has a pacemaker. Each recording is a 30-minute excerpt and
 403 contains the 12 standard leads. However four recordings have one lead that
 404 presents a constant value throughout its entire duration (recordings I2, I3, I57
 405 and I58; the constant leads are V6, V3, V4 and V4, respectively; see Fig 2).
 406 Although this is not a problem for the EEAC algorithm, since it can be applied
 407 over any number of leads, it would complicate the comparison of the results of
 408 applying the algorithm with different numbers of leads (the 12-lead tests would
 409 comprise 71 recordings, while the tests using from 1 to 10 would comprise 75
 410 recordings). Hence, these four recordings shall not be used in our tests.

411 All recordings were annotated by an automatic algorithm and later these
412 annotations were corrected manually by cardiologists. The annotations in this
413 database follow the beat classification proposed by the Association for the Ad-
414 vancement of Medical Instrumentation (AAMI) for evaluating the performance
415 of algorithms of heart rhythm analysis [15]. AAMI recommends a division of
416 beats into 5 types: normal heartbeat (N), supraventricular (S), ventricular (V),
417 fusion (F) and indeterminate (Q). This classification will be used in this paper
418 to evaluate the results of the clustering configurations.

419 4.2. Beat representation

420 Due to its robustness and compactness, we shall use a decomposition based
421 on the orthonormal Hermite functions to represent the beats. A 200 ms window
422 of samples around the beat position is extracted, and the regression coefficients
423 to represent the beat using 16 Hermite functions will be calculated. The feature
424 vector of each beat over a given lead will be made up by the 16 coefficients of
425 the Hermite decomposition, plus a parameter common to all the functions that
426 controls the width of the regression functions, 17 features overall (for details
427 see [30]). From the point of view of the EEAC algorithm, each of the 12 leads
428 will be considered as a data stream s_k , where $k = 1, 2, \dots, 12$. From each data
429 stream, the 17 features will be extracted.

430 The Hermite decomposition only captures information regarding the mor-
431 phology of the beat, while some types of arrhythmia such as premature atrial
432 contractions and escape beats differ not in their morphology, but in the dis-
433 tances between consecutive beats. To represent this information, we will use
434 an additional data stream s_{13} , made up by two features related to the distance
435 between beats that were inspired by [26]. For the beat o_i these features R_i^1 and
436 R_i^2 are defined as:

$$R_i^1 = T_i - T_{i-1}, \quad (14)$$

$$\Delta[i] = (T_{i+1} - T_i) - (T_i - T_{i-1}), \quad (15)$$

$$R_i^2 = u(\Delta[i]) \cdot \Delta[i],$$

437 being T_i the R-peak position of the beat o_i ; $\Delta[i]$ is the difference between the
438 distance from the i -th beat to the next one, and the distance from the i -th beat
439 to the previous one; $u(x)$ is the Heaviside step function and it used to remove
440 negative values of $\Delta[i]$ in Eq. (15).

441 4.3. Approaches for Generating Partitions

442 We will use 6 approaches to generate the partitions. The first three try
443 to achieve the best possible performance in the problem of morphological beat
444 grouping, while the other three are designed to analyze the properties of the
445 EEAC algorithm. In all cases the size of the vector V to store the summary
446 of the beats will be 300 (which approximately corresponds to 3-4 minutes of
447 ECG).

448 In approach 1, all the morphological features extracted from all the available
449 leads, and those given by Eqs. (14) and (15) are combined into a single feature
450 vector. The resulting feature vector for k leads has $k \times 17 + 2$ features; i.e., for
451 a single lead it would have 19 features, while for 12 it would have 206 features.
452 300 partitions will be created during initialization ($p_{init} = 300$), and 3 partitions
453 each time a new beat arrives ($p = 3$).

454 In approach 2, the features extracted from each lead make up a different
455 feature vector. There will be an additional feature vector made up by Eqs. (14)
456 and (15). For each feature vector, 300 partitions will be created during initial-
457 ization, and 3 each time a new beat arrives. In approaches 1 and 2 each feature
458 is used exactly the same number of times to extract evidence. However, ap-
459 proach 2 extracts evidence more times (using a subset of the available features
460 on each occasion) than in approach 1. For example, when using a single lead,
461 in approach 1 a single feature vector with 19 features will be constructed, and
462 evidence from it will be extracted 3 times for each new beat. In approach 2, two
463 feature vectors will be constructed (of size 17 and 2, respectively) and evidence
464 will be extracted 3 times from each vector, 6 times overall.

465 In approach 3 all available features are grouped into a single feature vector
466 (as in approach 1). For k leads, $(k+1) \times 300$ partitions will be created during ini-

467 tialization, and $(k + 1) \times 3$ partitions each time a new beat arrives (i.e., evidence
468 is extracted the same number of times as in approach 2). Therefore, evidence
469 from each feature is extracted a greater number of times than in approaches 1
470 or 2 (about an order of magnitude more times for the higher numbers of leads).
471 Approach 3 is designed to tease out the effects of working with smaller feature
472 vectors (approach 2 vs 3) and extracting evidence more times with the same
473 vectors (approach 1 vs 3).

474 It can be argued that approach 2 gives more weight to the beat distance
475 features than approaches 1 and 3. In this approach each feature vector provides
476 the same amount of evidence. Therefore, if a single lead is used, 1/2 of the
477 evidence comes from the 17 morphological features, and 1/2 comes from the 2
478 beat distance features. In approaches 1 and 3 there is a single feature vector
479 with 19 features, and the impact of the 2 distance features would be somewhat
480 lower, since they would be 2 features out of the 19 that are used to calculate
481 the Euclidean distance. Therefore, it can not be ruled out that differences in
482 performance between the approaches are due to the different treatment of the
483 beat distance features.

484 Approaches 4, 5 and 6 are analogous to approaches 1, 2 and 3, respectively,
485 being the only difference that they do not consider the beat distance features.
486 Hence, it is expected that none of these approaches will perform the best. How-
487 ever, they permit studying the algorithm’s behavior without being influenced
488 by the relevance that a certain features may have to address a specific problem.

489 To test the capability of integrating multiple data streams, for each approach
490 we run the algorithm using 1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12 leads. More leads means more
491 complementary information about the beats, and should enable better decisions.
492 However, working in a 206-dimensional feature space (as it happens in some of
493 the approaches for 12 leads) may degrade the performance of machine learning
494 algorithms. For the tests with fewer than 12 leads, the leads used in each test
495 are randomly chosen among the 12 leads available. In addition to this source of
496 randomness, the initialization of the K-means centroids is also random. Hence,
497 even when running the algorithm over the same leads, different results can be

Figure 3: Error rate and 95% confidence intervals for the EEAC algorithm for the three approaches that use the beat distance features, and for Clustream (CS) and Clustree (CT).

498 obtained. To take this into account, for each approach and lead number, the
 499 algorithm will be run 25 times.

500 According to our experience, better performance is obtained in beat cluster-
 501 ing if the proportion of evidence extracted from the morphological features
 502 is not more than twice the evidence extracted from the features derived from
 503 the beat distances [32]. To maintain this ratio, in approach 2 when using 4 or
 504 more leads, the number of times that evidence is extracted from these features
 505 is increased. This has also been taken into account in approach 3 to ensure that
 506 the number of times that evidence is extracted is equal to the total number of
 507 times that evidence is extracted in approach 2.

508 In all the cases, when extracting the final partition with the hierarchical
 509 linkage clustering, 25 clusters shall be used to enable a direct comparison with
 510 other ECG clustering papers which have used this number [10, 26, 32]. To

Table 1: Error rate and standard deviation for the three approaches that use the beat distance features for different numbers of ECG leads, and for Clustream and Clustree. * means that there is a statistically significant difference with the result obtained using the same approach for the immediately inferior number of leads.

Leads	Approach 1	Approach 2	Approach 3	Clustream	Clustree
1	1.722±0.253	0.735±0.116	1.321±0.216	1.018±0.186	1.042±0.080
2	1.391±0.150*	0.517±0.054*	0.872±0.092*	0.912±0.086*	0.960±0.049*
4	1.253±0.128*	0.390±0.033*	0.705±0.062*	0.884±0.077	0.867±0.030*
6	1.259±0.119	0.350±0.017*	0.656±0.050*	0.825±0.063*	0.859±0.027
8	1.275±0.107	0.333±0.019*	0.611±0.017*	0.831±0.044	0.856±0.027
10	1.308±0.083	0.320±0.015*	0.607±0.012	0.819±0.044	0.858±0.027
12	1.331±0.065	0.314±0.010	0.600±0.013*	0.843±0.032	0.878±0.021

Table 2: Error rate and standard deviation for the three approaches that do not use the beat distance features. * means that there is a statistically significant difference with the result obtained using the same approach for the immediately inferior number of leads.

Leads	Approach 4	Approach 5	Approach 6
1	1.756±0.228	1.770±0.256	1.745±0.301
2	1.447±0.145*	0.894±0.114*	1.012±0.119*
4	1.345±0.133*	0.653±0.054*	0.772±0.083*
6	1.338±0.113	0.581±0.042*	0.665±0.025*
8	1.360±0.119	0.565±0.032*	0.630±0.017*
10	1.356±0.074	0.540±0.011*	0.616±0.013*
12	1.378±0.054	0.532±0.009*	0.605±0.010*

511 evaluate the final partition, we shall consider that a cluster belongs to the type
512 of the majority of its beats, according to the INCARTDB annotations. All beats
513 in the cluster that are from a different type are considered errors.

514 5. Results

515 Table 1 and Figure 3 show the mean error rate and the standard deviation
516 of the 25 executions for each number of ECG leads of the approaches that use
517 the beat distance features, as well as for Clustream and Clustree. Table 2
518 and Figure 4 shows the same data for the approaches that did not use these
519 features. CluStream and ClusTree used weighted k-means to produce 25 macro-
520 clusters. Both algorithms were designed to work over a single stream; hence

Figure 4: Error rate and 95% confidence intervals for the EEAC algorithm for the three approaches that do not use beat distance features.

521 all features had to be gathered in a single feature vector. Their parameters
522 were tuned using Bayesian parameter search (25 trials based on Tree Parzen
523 Estimators [35]) which sought to minimize mean error rate for six leads. We
524 did not consider tuning for each different number of leads since the aim of the
525 tests was studying the dependency of the algorithm with the number of leads,
526 and since the same parameters were used for any number of leads in the EEAC
527 algorithm. The usage of six leads due to being the intermediate case, instead
528 of the more extreme cases of using a single lead or 12 leads. After parameter
529 tuning, error rates for each number of leads were estimated by running the
530 algorithms 25 times; in each run the leads were selected randomly.

531 Statistical tests were used to assess if the differences in error rate for each
532 approach when using different numbers of leads were significant. The Shapiro
533 test was used to check the normality of the data, and it was found that the
534 distributions of the errors were not always normal. Thus non-parametric tests
535 were used. The Friedman test was applied to check if the results obtained with
536 different number of leads for a given approach differ. They were found to differ
537 in all the cases (p -value < 0.001 in all cases).

538 For each approach, the results obtained for two consecutive number of leads
539 (i.e., 1 lead vs 2 leads, 2 leads vs 4 leads, 4 leads vs 6 leads, and so on) were
540 compared to assess the benefit of adding more leads. For that end, the Wilcoxon
541 test was used. In Tables 1 and 2 the comparisons that were statistically signifi-
542 cant (p -value < 0.05) have been marked with an *. In approach 2, the p -value
543 of the comparison of 10 vs 12 leads was 0.070; in approach 3, the comparison
544 of 8 vs 10, and 10 vs 12 yielded p -values of 0.141 and 0.029, respectively. For
545 approaches 5 and 6, all p -values were < 0.05 .

546 The best results for any number of leads were obtained for approach 2 (see
547 Table 1). The Wilcoxon test was used to compare the results of approach 2 with
548 the results of approach 1 and 3 using the same number of leads; all pairwise com-
549 parisons yielded p -values $< 10^{-9}$. The best results were obtained for approach
550 2 using 12 leads (0.314 ± 0.010). The confusion matrix was calculated for this
551 test using the annotations recommended by the AAMI [15] (see Table 3); the

552 original database annotations are shown in the columns. The overall sensitivity
 553 and positive predictive value of the algorithm are 99,50% and 99,59%.

554 The approaches that did not use beat distance information have a similar
 555 performance for 1 lead (pairwise comparisons of approaches 4 vs 5, 4 vs 6,
 556 and 5 vs 6 yielded p -values of 0.501, 0,732 and 0.679, respectively). This was
 557 expected, since these approaches are identical if a single data stream is available.
 558 For more than two leads, all pairwise comparisons among different approaches
 559 yielded p -values < 0.001 .

Table 3: Confusion matrix for approach 2 using 12 leads. ‘N’ stands for Normal heartbeat, ‘S’ for Supraventricular, ‘V’ for Ventricular (V), ‘F’ for Fusion, ‘Q’ for indeterminate, ‘Se’ for sensitivity and ‘P+’ for positive predictivity value.

	N	S	V	F	Q
N	145205	205	56	49	0
S	69	700	2	0	0
V	17	1	18976	61	0
F	5	0	28	98	0
Q	0	0	0	0	4
Se(%)	99.94	77.26	99.55	47.12	100
P+(%)	98.79	90.79	99.59	74.81	100

560 6. Discussion

561 This discussion will be organized in two sections. First, the application of the
 562 EEAC algorithm to the morphological identification of beats will be discussed
 563 using the results of Table 1. Then the properties of the EEAC algorithm will
 564 be discussed using the results of the Table 2, since these results enable a better
 565 study of the properties of the algorithm without being affected by the impact
 566 that a certain set of features has on a specific application.

567 6.1. Beat clustering

568 It can be seen from Figure 3 that the treatment of the beat distance has a
 569 considerable impact in the problem of morphological identification: the fact that
 570 approach 2 has a lower error rate than the other two for a single lead arises only

571 from the treatment of the beat distance as an independent data stream, instead
572 of being merged into a single feature vector with the morphological features.
573 Moreover, the error rates are higher when the beat distance features are not
574 used (compare approaches 1 vs 4, 2 vs 5, and 3 vs 6 in Tables 1 and 2).

575 The results obtained by the EEAC algorithm using approach 2 and 12 leads
576 in the task of morphological beat identification are good compared to the results
577 of other authors. Lagerholm et al. [26] obtained an error rate of 1.23% when
578 clustering the beats in 25 clusters, the same number of clusters used in this
579 work. Castro et al. developed one of the few algorithms for dynamic beat
580 clustering available in the literature [10]. They also used 25 clusters, obtaining
581 an error rate of 1.16%. Chen et al. also developed a dynamic algorithm for
582 morphological beat identification [11], and they reported an error rate of 1.54%.
583 However, comparison with present results should be performed with caution,
584 since those works have used a different database for their evaluation: the MIT-
585 BIH Arrhythmia Database, which comprises 48 recordings that only have 2 ECG
586 leads (the INCARTDB used in this work has 71 recordings with 12 leads).

587 There are several authors who have used the INCARTDB in the evaluation.
588 Kalidas and Tamil [23] developed an algorithm that uses semisupervised au-
589 toencoders and random forests to identify ventricular beats, and they achieved
590 a sensitivity of 88.08% and a positive predictive value of 94.76%, compared
591 with 99,55% y 99,59% in our approach (see Table 3). Al Rahhal et al. [2] built
592 a classifier from an interactive ensemble learning approach obtaining an error of
593 0.3%, although this algorithm is static and requires that a cardiologist manually
594 labels 200 beats from each recording. Llamedo and Martínez [28] used quadratic
595 discriminant classifiers, obtaining an error rate of 9.38%.

596 In the clinical routine, arrhythmia identification is carried out using 12 leads,
597 since each of them provides complementary information. However, it can be
598 found in the literature on automatic arrhythmia identification that only one
599 or two leads are typically used [1, 11, 26], even when working with databases
600 that have more leads available [3, 23, 44]. Adding more leads increments the
601 number of dimensions of the feature space used for beat representation; using

602 12 leads increases 12 fold the dimensionality compared to using a single lead.
603 High dimensionality feature spaces often decrease the performance of machine
604 learning techniques [17]; hence most authors opt for using one or two leads.
605 When all the features are gathered in a single vector (approach 1), as well as
606 with the Clustream and Clustree algorithms, it can be observed that after 4-6
607 leads there are no statistically significant decreases in the error rate, and it even
608 begins to increase (see Table 1). However, when the EEAC algorithm works
609 with the features of each stream separately, the error rate continues to decrease
610 up to 12 leads, being these decreases statistically significant up to 10 leads (the
611 p -value of 10 vs 12 leads was 0.070). We believe that the success in exploiting the
612 information from the 12 leads lays on its capability to avoid high dimensional
613 feature spaces by modeling each lead as an independent data stream.

614 Llamedo et al. [27] is one of the few works that takes advantage of 12 leads
615 of the INCARTDB, where the authors applied principal component analysis
616 over the features extracted from the 12 leads to reduce the number of dimen-
617 sions. Then they applied linear discriminant classifiers, obtaining an error rate of
618 2.88%. 12 leads are also used in [32], obtaining an error rate of 0.338% (slightly
619 worse than the one obtained in this work). This work used 25 groups and strate-
620 gies for generating evidence quite similar to those of this work. However, being
621 a static algorithm, it assumes that all data is available from the beginning, and
622 it works directly over the feature vectors of the beats, instead of over a proto-
623 type array summarizing the beats. When working over a prototype array, some
624 information on the beats is lost, and a poorer performance would be expected.
625 We believe that the slightly better performance obtained here arises from the
626 fact that, due to its dynamic nature, the EEAC algorithm extracts evidence
627 more times. In [32] evidence is extracted 300 times from each lead using all the
628 beats present in the recording. In approach 2 of this work, after initialization,
629 evidence is extracted 3 times each time a new beat arrives using the 300-size
630 prototype array. This means that evidence is extracted over 6000 times from
631 each recording, instead of 300 times. We believe that extracting evidence more
632 times compensates working over the prototype array instead of over the original

633 feature vectors. Note that extracting evidence more times does not mean that
634 the EEAC algorithm has less performance. Both algorithms have a computa-
635 tional complexity that is quadratic in the number of objects used to extract
636 evidence, and linear in the number of times that evidence is extracted. This
637 prevents the algorithm presented in [32] to be applied over long-term recordings,
638 such as Holter recordings, which often contain several hundred thousand beats.
639 However, the EEAC algorithm can handle such recordings since it works on a
640 constant size array of prototypes.

641 *6.2. EEAC algorithm*

642 The results of Table 2 show that the strategy of collecting evidence inde-
643 pendently from the feature vector of each lead is superior to the strategy of
644 extracting evidence from a single feature vector built by grouping all the fea-
645 tures (see approaches 4 vs 5). In Approach 4, when a second lead is added, the
646 benefit of the additional information provided by that lead is partially offset
647 by the increase in the number of dimensions of the feature space over which
648 K-means is applied to extract the evidence: it goes from 17 to 34 dimensions.
649 This is the reason why the error is reduced much less in approach 4 when going
650 from 1 to 2 leads, compared to approach 5. In this second case, we continue
651 working with 17-dimensional feature vectors, and the algorithm is more success-
652 ful when exploiting the new data stream (the new lead). In both approaches 4
653 and 1, after using 4-6 leads, the error rate begins to slightly increase (although
654 this increase is not statistically significant). In contrast, in approaches 2 and 5,
655 the error rate continues to decrease as new leads are added. This happens de-
656 spite the fact that in all these approaches each feature is used exactly the same
657 number of times to extract evidence. We hypothesize that this occurs because
658 K-means is more likely to get stuck in a local minimum the more dimensions
659 the feature space has. When getting stuck in a local minimum, the partition
660 found by K-means is less likely to reflect the natural partition of the data, and
661 therefore the evidence extracted is of poorer quality. Note that the dimension
662 of the feature space on which K-means is applied in approach 4 goes up to 204

663 for 12 leads, while it remains at 17 in approach 5 for any number of leads.

664 Approach 6 (and 3), despite working on feature vectors of the same dimen-
665 sion as approach 4 (and 1), continues to present decreases in the error rate
666 when the number of leads increases. However, these decreases are of a lesser
667 magnitude than the ones of approach 2 (and 5): note the error rate obtained
668 for one lead for approaches 5 and 6 in Table 2 (p -value=0.679) and for 12 leads
669 (p -values $< 10^{-9}$). Approach 6 (and 3) extracts evidence a much higher number
670 of times than the rest of the approaches (36 times per new beat for 12 leads,
671 instead of 3 times). We believe that by extracting evidence more times the
672 ensemble algorithm can partially compensate poorer quality of the K-means
673 partitions obtained in the high dimensionality feature spaces. However, note
674 that the computational complexity of the EEAC algorithm increases linearly
675 with the number of times evidence is extracted (see Eq. 13), and that better
676 results are still obtained when working with smaller feature vectors (approach 5
677 vs 6), despite evidence been extracted an order magnitude less times per feature
678 (3 times vs 36 times).

679 Traditional dimensional reduction techniques such as PCA are typically not
680 suitable for data stream analysis since changes in data distributions of the
681 stream can cause the importance of different features to vary over time [4, 36].
682 The results of Tables 1 and 2 indicate that the strategy of working separately
683 with the features extracted from each data stream can help handling high-
684 dimensional feature spaces. When the features extracted from each stream are
685 used to build separate feature vectors (which never go beyond 17 features), the
686 error rate continues to decrease when new data streams are added. But, when
687 all the features are used to build a single vector (of up to 206 features) the error
688 rate stops decreasing and it even gets worse.

689 The computational complexity of the EEAC algorithm is quadratic relative
690 to the size of the prototype array l , and linear in the rest of the parameters that
691 affect its performance (see Eq. 13). Therefore, this parameter must be chosen
692 with care. A value of l too small could prevent the creation of a sufficiently
693 detailed summary of the data to generate partitions that reflect the true struc-

694 ture of the data. Conversely, a very high value could decrease the performance
695 of the algorithm. For performance considerations, in some applications it may
696 be feasible an implementation of the algorithm where evidence is not extracted
697 every time a new object o^n arrives, but it waits until a batch of new objects are
698 available and evidence can be extracted for all of them together.

699 The computational complexity of the operations to be carried out each time
700 a new object arrives does not depend on the number of objects that have been
701 processed up to that moment (see Eq. 13). But storage requirements increase
702 linearly with this number: every time a new object arrives a new position has to
703 be added to the vector Y used to maintain the mapping between the l elements
704 of V and the n objects of O^n . Each position of Y only contains an integer,
705 but in a open-ended stream this increase would eventually deplete the storage
706 space. This problem can be avoided if older objects are discarded once they are
707 no longer relevant to the application, and their mapping information is deleted.
708 This could be achieved simply by replacing the vector V by a cyclic buffer.

709 In some cases, a data stream may be deemed by the data analyst as more
710 important when making decisions. In these cases, it might be advisable to
711 extract evidence a greater number of times from the most relevant data stream
712 (or streams). Hence, instead of generating a constant number of partitions p
713 for all data streams (see Eq. 13), a different number of partitions p_k would be
714 generated for each stream s_k . This situation has arisen in application to the
715 morphological beat identification. When using 4 or more leads, more partitions
716 are extracted for the beat distance between features, since experimentally we
717 have seen that this produces better results than extracting the same proportion
718 of evidence, due to the relative dilution of the evidence extracted from the
719 distance features when there is a high number of leads.

720 Concept drift might occur when analyzing data streams; i.e. the properties
721 of the data streams can vary over time. Gradual changes should be tracked by
722 the EEAC algorithm through the changes in the elements of V . When a new
723 object arrives the two most similar elements of V , v_i and v_j , are merged into
724 v_i , while the new object is stored directly in v_j . Hence, v_i represents at least

725 two objects (and probably more if the algorithm has been running for a long
726 time) while v_j represents a single object that has just arrived. Even if when
727 o_{n+1} arrives, $v_j = o_n$ is one of the elements that is going to be merged to make
728 room for o_{n+1} , the merger is carried out using an unweighted average (line 8) of
729 v_j (which currently represents a single object) with another element of V that
730 likely represents multiple objects. Hence, the elements of V put more emphasis
731 on the representation of the most recent objects, which helps the algorithm
732 respond to concept drift scenarios. However, in the presence of concept shift
733 resulting in the appearance or disappearance of a cluster, the EEAC algorithm
734 would likely merge or split some of the previous clusters of the final partition.
735 It would be desirable for the algorithm to have the ability to vary the number
736 of clusters when needed. However, the EEAC algorithm works with a fixed
737 number of clusters, this being one of the current limitations of the algorithm.
738 This situation may be alleviated by the fact that the user could manually cut
739 the dendrogram at a different height to obtain a different number of clusters.

740 **7. Conclusions**

741 We have presented an evolving clustering algorithm, named Evolving Evi-
742 dence Accumulation Clustering (EEAC), that is based on the evidence accu-
743 mulation paradigm. Each algorithm of the ensemble extracts evidence from a
744 single data stream; hence it can process multiple data streams without com-
745 bining their features into a single feature vector. To this end, K-means is run
746 several times with different parameters over a feature vector extracted from the
747 stream, obtaining several partitions of the data. Evidence is extracted from
748 these partitions through a voting mechanism in which the co-occurrence of two
749 objects in the same cluster of a partition is a vote towards both objects be-
750 ing together in the final partition. All votes of the ensemble are gathered in
751 a similarity matrix. If one of the data streams is not available (for example,
752 due to a malfunction in a sensor), or its data arrives late (for example, due to
753 network delays), no votes are obtained from it, but the final partition can still

754 be obtained using the available evidence at any time. The dynamic behavior is
755 achieved by extracting evidence over a fixed size vector that stores a represen-
756 tative summary of the objects up to the present time. Every time a new object
757 arrives, the two most similar beats in the vector are combined into an average
758 beat, leaving room for the new object.

759 The algorithm is highly parallelizable and suitable for distributed and col-
760 laborative implementations of the ensemble, lending itself well to edge-oriented
761 computing architectures [47]. In such scenario, the ensemble algorithms in
762 charge of processing the same data stream can run on a node located near
763 the sensor that collects the data, and only the evidence extracted needs to be
764 transmitted to a central node. This node would combine it with the evidence
765 obtained from the other nodes to obtain the final partition.

766 An additional advantage of the strategy of working separately with the
767 data of each stream is that it avoids problems derived from working in a high-
768 dimensional feature space. The results of Tables 1 and 2 show how this strategy
769 outperforms grouping all the features in a single vector, even when evidence
770 is extracted a much larger number of times from the single vector. This is a
771 remarkable feature of EEAC that allows it to exploit data redundancy, merging
772 data from multiple streams without degrading its performance.

773 The algorithm was applied to the morphological beat identification in real
774 time over the 12-lead Holter ECG recordings of the St.Petersburg Institute of
775 Cardiological Technics Arrhythmia Database, achieving a $0.314\% \pm 0.010$ error
776 rate when all 12 leads were used. The strategies of combining all leads in a
777 single feature vector or working with each lead independently were compared,
778 obtaining statistically significant better results in the second case. Tests also
779 were run where the EEAC algorithm used an increasing number of leads (from
780 1 up to 12). The more leads available, the lower error rate was obtained. It
781 should be noted that most authors that work with this database only use one
782 or two of the available leads, with the exception of [27], probably to avoid the
783 problem derived from working in high dimensionality feature spaces.

784 In its current form, the EEAC algorithm requires the user to specify a con-

stant number of clusters to extract in the final partition. It would be desirable that this number was estimated by the algorithm, and could evolve over time [22, 29]. We believe this may be achieved by using strategies based on cluster stability in the dendrogram, similar to those proposed in [33]. Our future work will be oriented in this direction. We also plan to work on strategies that permit associating a cluster of the final partition with the most similar clusters of the previous partitions, in order to track concept drift explicitly [31].

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